

A Comprehensive Fuzzy Model for Cost Optimization in Supply Chain Management

Sindhu. R. Dhavale^{1*}, Gajanan. C.Lomte^{2*}

1,2. School of Basic and Applied Science, M.G.M, University Chhatrapati Sambhajinagar- 431004 (M.S.)

*Corresponding Author: Sindhu. R. Dhavale

Abstract

To develop a comprehensive model that optimizes material costs, transportation costs, and inventory holding costs while accounting for uncertainties in facility capacities using fuzzy numbers. We propose a fuzzy mathematical program and compare its solution using the α -cut approach. The model captures uncertainties with trapezoidal fuzzy membership functions for cost coefficients, customer demand, and supplier warehouse capacity. A possibility programming approach transforms the fuzzy model into its deterministic equivalent. The model is tested using LINDO software on a simulated dataset. The model significantly enhances supply chain efficiency by identifying optimal procurement, transportation, and inventory strategies under uncertain conditions. The results demonstrate the feasibility and effectiveness of fuzzy mathematical programming and the α -cut solution approach in SCM, offering superior performance over traditional deterministic models by accommodating uncertainties. The model effectively reduces costs and improves operational flexibility, providing a novel and practical solution for real-life supply chain management challenges.

Keywords: Supply Chain Management, Fuzzy Linear Programming, Transportation Inventory Model, α -cut Approach, Cost Optimization, Uncertainty.

1. Introduction:

In today's world, enterprises have to handle the growing markets and the increasing competitive environment and customer expectation in this regard supply chain management is one of the important research area that has attracted the attention of enterprise managers and academic communities. We define a supply chain as an integrated process where different business entities such as suppliers, manufacture, distributors and retailers work together to plan, coordinate and control flow of materials, parts and finished goods from supplier to customer. This chain usually characterises by the forward flow of material and backward flow of information. Supply chain management often faces challenges due to imprecise data. Traditional methods like linear programming aim to optimize supply and demand but can't always handle the uncertainties in real-world scenarios. These uncertainties arise mainly from variations in demand, supply, and manufacturing processes. To tackle this, we use fuzzy logic, which employs membership functions to evaluate how satisfactory each potential solution is. The best solution maximizes satisfaction by effectively dealing with these uncertainties. This paper introduces a fuzzy linear programming model that uses α -cut techniques to enhance decision-making in supply chains, offering a practical approach for managing unpredictable elements.

In this context, several studies have been conducted, among which Gupta et al. [1] is notable. This study optimizes supply chain networks (SCN) using fuzzy goal programming (FGP) to address inefficiencies and achieve multiple objectives in an intuitionistic fuzzy environment.

The approach involves a bi-level decision-making process, where first-level decision-makers (FLDMs) focus on minimizing transportation costs, while second-level decision-makers (SLDMs) work on reducing delivery times and balancing allocations. The methodology is validated through a real-life case study. The FGP-based model provides a robust solution for enhancing SCN efficiency in complex, uncertain environments. Babagolzadeh et al. [2] present a multi-objective fuzzy programming model aimed at designing a sustainable supply chain network, considering disruptions. This model integrates sustainability with the robustness of supply chains, ensuring resilience against potential disruptions. Bas and Ozkok [3] introduce a fuzzy approach to a multi-objective mixed-integer linear programming model for a multi-echelon closed-loop supply chain with multiple products and time periods. This research emphasizes the integration of closed-loop systems and the handling of multiple time periods, adding depth to the optimization techniques in supply chain management. Alavidoost et al. [4] propose a novel fuzzy mathematical model for integrated supply chain planning using a multi-objective evolutionary algorithm. Their work enhances the understanding of evolutionary algorithms in optimizing complex supply chain networks. Ahmadini et al. [5] focus on sustainable green supply chains, addressing multi-objective optimization in inventory and production management. Their study is significant for its emphasis on sustainability in supply chain operations, aligning with contemporary environmental concerns. Badhotiya et al. [6] discuss fuzzy multi-objective optimization for multi-site integrated production and distribution planning in a two-echelon supply chain. This study provides insights into the complexities of multi-site production and distribution planning, crucial for efficient supply chain management. Ali et al. [7] use a fuzzy non-linear programming approach to address the measurements of perishable supply chains in a multi-product multi-echelon context. This research is vital for industries dealing with perishable goods, highlighting the need for precision in supply chain measurements. Shafipour-omran et al. [8] explore supply chain problems using fuzzy goal programming based on TOPSIS and fuzzy preference relations. Their dual approach provides a comparative analysis of fuzzy goal programming techniques, enhancing decision-making processes in supply chains. Adjei et al. [9] introduce fuzzy multi-objective mathematical modeling for distribution planning. Their work is timely, given the disruptions caused by the pandemic, and offers solutions for more resilient distribution planning. Varshney et al. [10] address uncertainty in closed-loop supply chain networks with a multi-objective approach to integrated production and transportation problems. Their study is particularly relevant for industries facing significant uncertainties and needing robust supply chain solutions. Amin-Tahmasbi et al. [11] present a multi-objective integrated optimization model for facility location and order allocation problems in a two-level supply chain network. This research is crucial for optimizing both facility locations and order allocations, which are pivotal for efficient supply chain operations. Kousar et al. [12] propose a multi-objective intuitionistic fuzzy linear programming model for optimizing industrial closed-loop supply chain networks. Their study focuses on closed-loop supply chains, contributing to the sustainable management of industrial networks. Mardanya et al. [13] address bi-level multi-objective transportation problems under fuzziness. This study provides insights into handling transportation issues at multiple levels of decision-making, which is critical for comprehensive supply chain management. Shafiee et al. [14] present a robust multi-objective optimization model for inventory and production management with environmental and social considerations. Their case study in the dairy industry demonstrates the practical applicability of their model in real-world scenarios, emphasizing sustainability and social responsibility. Simchi-Levi et al. [15] provide a

comprehensive guide on designing and managing supply chains, covering essential concepts, strategies, and real-world case studies. Their work serves as a foundational reference for understanding the complexities and best practices in supply chain management. Grubisic et al. [16] apply linear programming to land allocation in vegetable production, using a case study from Croatia. Their approach highlights the practical applications of optimization techniques in agricultural supply chains, offering valuable insights into resource allocation and production planning. Cccola et al. [17] focus on optimizing resource flows across the entire supply chain, with a specific application in the dairy industry. Their study demonstrates the use of computational tools to enhance efficiency and reduce waste in supply chain operations. Singh and Goh [18] develop a multi-objective mixed-integer programming model for a pharmaceutical supply chain, addressing the need for balancing multiple objectives in complex supply networks. Their research provides a detailed analysis of how mixed-integer programming can be utilized to optimize supply chain performance in the pharmaceutical sector. Bhatia and Bhat [19] explore the operational aspects of agricultural supply chain management, offering an in-depth perspective on managing supply chains in the agriculture industry. Their study underscores the importance of operational efficiency and strategic planning in agricultural supply chains. Taylor and Murphy [20] investigate sustainability practices and optimization in supply chains, proposing a model for green logistics. Their work is significant in the context of increasing environmental concerns, offering strategies for integrating sustainability into supply chain management. Shaltayev [21] presents a mixed-integer linear programming optimization model for the Supply Chain Game, demonstrating the application of optimization techniques in educational contexts. This study provides insights into how theoretical models can be applied in practical, game-based scenarios to enhance learning outcomes. Cao and Wang [22] develop a multi-objective multiperiod mixed-integer programming optimization model for integrated scheduling of supply chains under demand uncertainty. Their research addresses the challenges of demand variability, proposing solutions to optimize scheduling and resource allocation in uncertain environments. Zhou et al. [23] design a fuzzy bi-objective closed-loop supply chain network with multiple recovery options, focusing on sustainability and efficiency. Their study highlights the importance of closed-loop systems in supply chain management, offering innovative solutions for sustainable operations.

In summary, these studies collectively advance the field of multi-objective optimization in supply chains, addressing various challenges and proposing innovative solutions. The integration of fuzzy logic, sustainability considerations, and robust optimization techniques across different supply chain dimensions highlights the dynamic and evolving nature of this research area. Designing a supply chain network in a complex environment that provides an optimal platform for the effective and efficient supply chain management. To the best of my knowledge, there is a little research for solving supply chain design problem in fuzzy environment using alpha cut solution approach. The remainder of our work is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the mathematical formulation, incorporating fuzzy concepts and models. Section 3 provides a numerical example to illustrate the effectiveness of the proposed methodology. The results and discussion are detailed in Section 4, followed by the conclusion in Section 5.

2. Multi stage supply chain model:

In this study, a multi-echelon model is developed with the goal of minimizing total costs. The model considers a two-stage supply chain, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Two stage supply chain network

2.1 Model formulation

Notation

i : index for supplier

j : index for Warehouses

k : index for customer location

Parameter:

TC_{ij} : Transportation cost per unit from Supplier i to Warehouse j

TC_{jk} : Transportation cost per unit from Warehouse j to Customer k

IHC_j : Inventory Holding cost at Warehouse j

s_i : The Space required for each unit

p_j : The total available space in the Warehouse j

a_i : Capacity of the Supplier

b_j : Demand from warehouse j

c_k : Demand from Customer k

QM_{ij} : Quantity transported from Supplier i to warehouse j

WM_{jk} : Quantity transported Warehouses j to Customer k

e_j : Excess quantity of inventory at warehouse j

Π : Possibility measure

Transportation and Inventory Linear Programming Problem is (TILP) is given below,

2.2 Assumptions of the Model:

- 1] The demands for goods at customer location is Non Deterministic.
- 2] The capacities of supplier, warehouses and customer locations are not fixed
- 3] No lead times

Objective function

Min Z = transportation cost from Supplier to warehouse + Transportation cost from warehouse to customer + Inventory holding cost at warehouse

$$\min Z = \left[\sum_i \sum_j (TC_{ij} * QM_{ij}) + \sum_j \sum_k (TC_{jk} * WM_{jk}) + \sum_j (IHC_j * e_j) \right] \quad (1)$$

Subject to constraint

1. Supplier capacity constraint

$$\sum_j QM_{ij} = a_i \quad \forall i \quad (2)$$

2. Constraint for inventory and demand is

$$\sum_i QM_{ij} - e_j \leq b_j \quad \forall j \quad (3)$$

3. constraint for available space at warehouse is

$$\sum_i QM_{ij} * s_i \leq p_j \quad \forall k \quad (4)$$

4. Customer zone demand constraint

$$\sum_j WM_{jk} \geq c_k \quad \forall k \quad (5)$$

Non - Negativity constraint

All decision variables must be non-negativity

$$QM_{ij}, WM_{jk}, e_j \geq 0 \quad \forall i, j, k \quad (6)$$

2.3. Fuzzy Transportation Inventory Model

Min Z

Subject to constraint

$$\Pi [\sum_i \sum_j (\widetilde{TC}_{ij} * QM_{ij}) + \sum_j \sum_k \widetilde{TC}_{jk} * WM_{jk}) + \sum_j (\widetilde{IHC}_j * e_j) \leq Z] \leq \alpha_1$$

$$\Pi (\sum_j WM_{jk} \geq \widetilde{c}_k) \leq \alpha_2$$

$$\Pi (\sum_i QM_{ij} - e_j \geq \widetilde{b}_j) \leq \alpha_3$$

$$\Pi (\sum_j QM_{ij} \geq \widetilde{a}_i) \leq \alpha_4$$

$$\Pi (\sum_i QM_{ij} * s_i \geq \widetilde{p}_j) \leq \alpha_5$$

$$\sum_j QM_{ij} = a_i \quad \forall i$$

$$\sum_i QM_{ij} - e_j \leq b_j \quad \forall j$$

$$\sum_i QM_{ij} * s_i \leq p_j \quad \forall k$$

$$\sum_j WM_{jk} \geq c_k \quad \forall k$$

2.4. α -cut Solution Approach for Fuzzy Transportation and Inventory linear programming model

In the α -cut solution approach, the fuzzy transportation and inventory parameters are converted into a form that can be handled by traditional linear programming methods by transforming them into crisp values using α -cuts. This transforms the fuzzy model into the Possibility Transportation Inventory Linear Programming (PTILP) model.

Min z

Subject to constraint

$$[\sum_i \sum_j (\widetilde{TC}_{ij})_{\alpha_1}^L * QM_{ij} + \sum_j \sum_k (\widetilde{TC}_{jk})_{\alpha_1}^L * WM_{jk}) + \sum_j (\widetilde{IHC}_j)_{\alpha_1}^L * e_j \leq Z]$$

$$\sum_j WM_{jk} \geq (\widetilde{c}_k)_{\alpha_2}^L$$

$$\sum_i QM_{ij} - e_j \geq (\widetilde{b}_j)_{\alpha_3}^L$$

$$\sum_j QM_{ij} \geq (\widetilde{a}_i)_{\alpha_4}^L$$

$$\sum_j QM_{ij} * s_i \geq (\widetilde{p}_j)_{\alpha_5}^L$$

$$\sum_j QM_{ij} = a_i \quad \forall i$$

$$\sum_i QM_{ij} - e_j \leq b_j \quad \forall j$$

$$\sum_i QM_{ij} * s_i \leq p_j \quad \forall k$$

$$\sum_j WM_{jk} \geq c_k \quad \forall k$$

In the model, $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4$ and α_5 represent acceptable risk levels and are also used as alpha cut levels to transform associated fuzzy numbers into crisp values. The notation $(\cdot)_{\alpha_k}^L$ indicates the lower bounds of the α_k level associated with fuzzy variables. For example, $(\widetilde{TC}_{ij})_{\alpha_1}^L$ denotes the lower bounds of the fuzzy number \widetilde{TC}_{ij} at α_1 level, which depends on the membership function of the fuzzy parameters in the model. The fuzzy data may lead to nonlinear constraints related to the model, which can take linear or nonlinear forms. In this model, we utilize trapezoidal fuzzy numbers, as illustrated in Figure 2

Fig.2. Trapezoidal fuzzy number

Figure 2. illustrates how a trapezoidal fuzzy number can be transformed into an interval number $d = [\alpha * d_2 + (1-\alpha) * d_1, \alpha * d_3 + (1-\alpha) * d_4]$ using alpha cut techniques. By applying trapezoidal fuzzy numbers, the PTILP model is reduced to a Nonlinear Transportation and Inventory Linear Programming model (NTILP).

Min Z

Subjected to

$$\begin{aligned} & (1 - \alpha_1) \sum_i \sum_j (\widetilde{TC}_{ij})_1^L * QM_{ij} + \alpha_1 \sum_i \sum_j (\widetilde{TC}_{ij})_2^L * QM_{ij} + (1 - \alpha_1) \sum_j \sum_k (\widetilde{TC}_{jk})_1^L * \\ & WM_{jk} + \alpha_1 \sum_j \sum_k (\widetilde{TC}_{jk})_2^L * WM_{jk} + (1 - \alpha_1) \sum_j (\widetilde{IHC}_j)_1^L * e_j + \alpha_1 \sum_j (\widetilde{IHC}_j)_2^L * e_j \leq Z \\ & \sum_j WM_{jk} \geq (1 - \alpha_2) (\widetilde{c}_k)_1^L + \alpha_2 (\widetilde{c}_k)_2^L \\ & \sum_j QM_{ij} - e_j \leq (1 - \alpha_3) (\widetilde{b}_j)_1^L + \alpha_3 (\widetilde{b}_j)_2^L \\ & \sum_j QM_{ij} = (1 - \alpha_4) (\widetilde{a}_i)_1^L + \alpha_4 (\widetilde{a}_i)_2^L \\ & \sum_j QM_{ij} * s_i \geq (1 - \alpha_5) (\widetilde{p}_j)_1^L + \alpha_5 (\widetilde{p}_j)_2^L \sum_j QM_{ij} = a_i \quad \forall i \\ & \sum_i QM_{ij} - e_j \leq b_j \quad \forall j \end{aligned}$$

$$\sum_i QM_{ij} * s_i \leq p_j \forall k$$

$$\sum_j WM_{jk} \geq c_k \forall k$$

3. Numerical Example

We present a numerical example to illustrate the model. The model is applied to simulated data, and the supply chain network includes four suppliers, four warehouses, and six customer zones. The company procures raw materials from the four suppliers, stores them in the warehouses, and then dispatches them directly to the customer zones. The input data required for designing the supply chain for this industry is provided below.

Table 1. Transportation cost (from supplier to warehouse) per unit

Warehouse Suppliers	W ₁	W ₂	W ₃	W ₄
S ₁	[14,15,16,17]	[13,14,15,16]	[13,15,16,17]	[19,20,21,23]
S ₂	[12,13,14,16]	[15,16,17,19]	[17,18,19,21]	[14,15,17,18]
S ₃	[18,20,21,22]	[30,32,35,36]	[18,19,20,22]	[12,14,16,18]
S ₄	[16,17,18,20]	[13,15,17,19]	[17,19,21,22]	[32,34,36,38]

Table 2. Transportation cost (from Warehouse to Customer) per unit

Customer Warehouse	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₅	C ₆
W ₁	[12,14,15,16]	[19,22,23,25]	[15,16,17,18]	[16,17,18,20]	[17,18,19,20]	[22,24,25,26]
W ₂	[18,20,21,22]	[12,14,16,17]	[18,22,23,24]	[19,22,25,26]	[20,23,26,28]	[21,22,23,26]
W ₃	[34,36,38,40]	[21,22,25,26]	[25,26,28,32]	[22,24,26,40]	[21,22,27,29]	[16,17,18,19]
W ₄	[19,20,22,24]	[16,18,20,21]	[20,22,23,27]	[17,19,20,24]	[22,23,26,28]	[21,22,24,28]

Table 3. Inventory holding cost per unit

Warehouse	Inventory holding cost
W ₁	[10,11,12,13]
W ₂	[12,13,15,18]
W ₃	[10.4,10.5,10.7,10.9]
W ₄	[10.8,10.9,11,11.5]

Table 4. Warehouse Demand and storage capacity

Warehouse	Demand	Storage Capacity
W ₁	[120,135,165,180]	[200,225,275,300]
W ₂	[140,157.5,192.5,210]	[280,315,385,420]
W ₃	[160,180,220,240]	[200,225,275,300]
W ₄	[140,157.5,192.5,210]	[240,270,330,360]

Table 5. Customer Demand

C ₁	[55,60,62,65]
C ₂	[80.84,86,88]
C ₃	[105,110,115,120]
C ₄	[55,58,60,65]
C ₅	[85,90,95,98]
C ₆	[130,135,141,142]

Table 6. Supplier capacity

Supplier	Capacity
S ₁	[160,180,220,240]
S ₂	[200,225,275,300]
S ₃	[140,157.5,192.5,210]
S ₄	[180,202.5,247.5,270]

4. Results and Discussions

The linear programming problem was solved using the LINDO software, defining the objective function and constraints according to the fuzzy transportation inventory model. The numerical values for the decision variables were computed for different levels of α (0.1, 0.5, 0.9), representing different confidence levels in the fuzzy parameters. Results show that as the α levels increase, both quantities and costs rise, indicating greater confidence in meeting constraints. Specifically, the objective values increase from 17,434 at $\alpha = 0.1$ to 20,704.38 at $\alpha = 0.9$, highlighting a clear trade-off between cost and risk. The model's flexibility enables decision-makers to choose suitable α levels according to their risk tolerance, optimizing the balance between cost efficiency and certainty.

Overall, the fuzzy transportation inventory model proves to be a flexible and practical tool for SCM, capable of accommodating uncertainties and providing more realistic solutions compared to traditional deterministic approaches. This research validates the model's feasibility and effectiveness, offering significant improvements in managing supply chain operations under uncertainty

Table 7. The solution for the numerical example is described as follows

Decision Variable	Linear Model	$\alpha = 0.1$	$\alpha = 0.5$	$\alpha = 0.9$
QM13	200	162	170	178
QM21	250	202.50	212.5	222.5
QM34	175	141.75	148.75	155.75
QM42	225	182.25	191.25	200.25
WM11	61	55.5	57.5	59.50
WM13	112.5	105.50	107.5	110.50
WM14	59	55.30	55.3	57.50
WM15	92.5	85.50	87.5	89.50
WM22	85	80.4	82	83.6
WM36	138	130.50	132.5	134.50
e_1	100	51	85	89
e_2	50	40.50	42.5	44.5
e_3	0	10.50	0	0

Fig. 3. The performance of crisp model and fuzzy models

Table 8. Results of the Global Criteria Method

A	Objective Value
0.1	17434
0.5	19161.83
0.9	20704.38

Fig. 4. The objective values for the model at different α levels

5. Conclusions

To handle the complexities and constraints of real-life environments in supply chain management (SCM), a deterministic mathematical program is insufficient. Therefore, we propose a fuzzy mathematical program and use the α -cut approach to compare their solutions. The fuzzy transportation inventory model is utilized to capture these uncertainties, expressing the flexibility of the proposed model in real-life scenarios. In this model, cost coefficients, customer demand, and supplier warehouse capacity are considered fuzzy with trapezoidal fuzzy membership functions. A possibility programming approach is employed to transform the fuzzy model into its equivalent deterministic form. The main advantage of a supply chain network with warehouse storage is its ability to reduce delivery costs and provide a faster response compared to other networks, making it particularly suitable for fast-moving items. Our findings indicate that as the value of the α -cut increases, transportation costs from supplier to warehouse and from warehouse to customer also rise. Additionally, the inventory holding cost at the warehouse increases with higher α -cut values.

A numerical example demonstrates the feasibility of the proposed model, showing that it provides the best and most efficient solution using the α -cut approach. This paper focuses on minimizing costs in supply chain networks using a fuzzy mathematical programming approach. It addresses decision-making under uncertain parameters that cannot be managed by conventional mathematical programming. The proposed model, solved using LINDO software, demonstrates that it offers a better approximation of real-life applications compared to traditional models.

References:

- [1] Gupta S, Haq A, Ali I, Sarkar B. Significance of multi-objective optimization in logistics problem for multi-product supply chain network under the intuitionistic fuzzy environment. *Complex & Intelligent Systems*. 2021 Aug;7(4):2119-39.
- [2] Babagolzadeh R, Rezaeian J, Khatir MV. Multi-objective fuzzy programming model to design a sustainable supply chain network considering disruption. *International Journal of Industrial Engineering & Production Research*. 2020 Jun 10;31(2):217-29.
- [3] Bas S, Ozkok B. A fuzzy approach to multi-objective mixed-integer linear programming model for multi-echelon closed-loop supply chain with multi-product multi-time period. *Operations Research and Decisions*. 2020;30(1).
- [4] Alavidoost MH, Jafarnejad A, Babazadeh H. A novel fuzzy mathematical model for an integrated supply chain planning using multi-objective evolutionary algorithm. *Soft Computing*. 2021 Feb;25(3):1777-801.
- [5] Ahmadini AA, Modibbo UM, Shaikh AA, Ali I. Multi-objective optimization modelling of sustainable green supply chain in inventory and production management. *Alexandria Engineering Journal*. 2021 Dec 1;60(6):5129-46.
- [6] Badhotiya GK, Soni G, Mittal ML. Fuzzy multi-objective optimization for multi-site integrated production and distribution planning in two echelon supply chain. *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*. 2019 May 19; 102:635-45.
- [7] Ali SS, Barman H, Kaur R, Tomaskova H, Roy SK. Multi-product multi-echelon measurements of perishable supply chain: Fuzzy non-linear programming approach. *Mathematics*. 2021 Aug 30;9(17): 2093.
- [8] Shafipour-omran B, Khalili-Damghani K, Ghasemi P. Solving a supply chain problem using two approaches of fuzzy goal programming based on TOPSIS and fuzzy preference relations. *Journal of Industrial and Systems Engineering*. 2020 Nov 20;13(2):27-48.
- [9] Adjei P, Careaga-Campos A, Suer G, Alhawari O. Fuzzy multi-objective mathematical modelling for distribution planning. In *Intelligent and Transformative Production in Pandemic Times: Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on Production Research*; 2023 Feb 3. Cham: Springer International Publishing. pp. 357-366.
- [10] Varshney N, Gupta S, Ahmed A. Addressing uncertainty in closed-loop supply chain networks: a multi-objective approach to integrated production and transportation problems. *Journal of Modelling in Management*. 2024 Apr 30.
- [11] Amin-Tahmasbi H, Sadafi S, Ekren BY, Kumar V. A multi-objective integrated optimisation model for facility location and order allocation problem in a two-level supply chain network. *Annals of Operations Research*. 2023 May;324(1):993-1022.
- [12] Kousar S, Batool M, Kausar N, Pamucar D, Ozbilge E, Tantay B. Multi-objective intuitionistic fuzzy linear programming model for optimization of industrial closed-loop supply chain network. *Advances in Production Engineering & Management*. 2022 Sep 1;17(3):381-93.
- [13] Mardanya D, Maity G, Roy SK. Solving bi-level multi-objective transportation problem under fuzziness. *International Journal of Uncertainty, Fuzziness and Knowledge-Based Systems*. 2021 Jun;29(03):411-33.
- [14] Shafiee F, Kazemi A, Chaghooshi AJ, Sazvar Z, Mahdiraji HA. A robust multi-objective optimization model for inventory and production management with environmental and social consideration: a real case of dairy industry. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 2021 Apr 20; 294:126230.
- [15] Simchi-Levi D, Kaminsky P, Simchi-Levi E. Designing and managing the supply chain: concepts, strategies, and case studies. 3rd ed. New York: McGraw-Hill; 2008.

- [16] Grubisic M, Kolarec B, Mamic M. A linear programming approach to land allocation in vegetable production: a case study from Croatia. *International Journal of Modeling and Optimization*. 2019;9(3).
- [17] Cocco ME, Basán N, Méndez CA, Dondo RG. Optimization of resource flows across the whole supply chain. Application to a case study in the dairy industry. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*. 2022; 158:107632.
- [18] Singh SK, Goh M. Multi-objective mixed integer programming and an application in a pharmaceutical supply chain. *International Journal of Production Research*. 2019 Feb 16;57(4):1214-37.
- [19] Bhatia M, Bhat G. Agriculture supply chain management-an operational perspective. *BJO&PM*. 2020 Oct 15 [cited 2024 May 13];17(4):1-18. Available from:
- [20] Taylor L, Murphy F. Sustainability practices and optimization in supply chains: a model for green logistics. *International Journal of Production Economics*. 2021; 231:107883.
- [21] Shaltayev D. Mixed-integer linear programming optimization for the supply chain game. *Decision Sciences Journal of Innovative Education*. 2021 Oct;19(4):250-64.
- [22] Cao W, Wang X. A multiobjective multiperiod mixed-integer programming optimization model for integrated scheduling of supply chain under demand uncertainty. *IEEE Access*. 2022 Jun 15; 10:63958-70.
- [23] Zhou J, Xia W, Wang K, Li H, Zhang Q. Fuzzy bi-objective closed-loop supply chain network design problem with multiple recovery options. *Sustainability*. 2020 Aug 20;12(17):6770.